

ROLES OF ADVERTISING

Alexandra IORGULESCU

Associate Professor, PhD, University of Craiova
ancaiorgulescu@yahoo.com

Abstract:

In this article I have focused on the importance of national publicity, publicity as an institution that has been studied for a long time in this century, both by critics and partisans. The perspectives on the roles of advertising generally fall into one of three categories: serving consumers, business and society, which are also briefly outlined in this article.

Keywords: advertising, consumers, business.

Introduction

National advertising

National advertising expression has a special non-geographical meaning in advertising: it refers to advertising by the owner of a service or product with a registered trademark (brand name) sold through different distributors, regardless of where they are located. It does not mean that the product is sold throughout the country. Traditionally, national advertising has been general in terms of product information. Items such as price, endetail availability and even service and installation are often omitted from national advertising or are mentioned in general terms. Instead, it often identifies a specific target audience and creates an image for the product.

While this general approach is still the rule, we are noticing companies that, while typically advertising nationally, are also approaching regional (in some cases even local) aspects of advertising. As research studies allow these companies to identify and cover specific market segments with greater precision, we will see more regionalised advertising. When this happens, companies that used to advertise nationally will be able to provide more information of interest to each segment, and national ads will reflect local advertising approaches in their content. However, in the short term, national advertising will continue to reflect the introduction of new product brands and greater loyalty to existing product brands.

Advertising as an institution

Advertising is more than a means of disseminating product information. It is a primary communication tool of our economic system and culture. In many ways, advertising reflects contemporary society and more of a particular period. For example, 25 years ago, advertising largely portrayed a white, masculine, middle-class society, ignoring minorities or women presented in a secondary role. Today, advertising, like our society, is much more sensitive and realistic in its treatment of different people. It is not uncommon today to see an advertisement in which a woman appears as a hospital director, car buyer or business traveller. Minorities are also portrayed more often and in a more realistic and positive light than ever before. Advertising reflects the society in which it operates, and at the same time it gives rise to subtle changes in the mores and behaviour of the public that receives it. No wonder advertising is one of the most researched commercial methods.

Advertising has a moral and ethical responsibility to deal honestly with the portrayal of society, but it is also a good business. Different companies are judged by their own advertising, and the effectiveness of advertising depends on the general attitude of consumers towards advertising in general. One study has shown that the extent to which people pay attention to a particular advertisement is influenced by their opinion of advertising as an institution. "The value that advertising has for a particular commercial brand depends on the extent to which the consumer believes that advertising is informative and fair in general" (A. Mehta, S.C. Purvis).

The role of advertising as an institution has been studied for most of this century by critics and partisans alike. Perspectives on the roles of advertising generally fall into one of three categories: what advertising does for consumers, for business and for society.

The role of advertising for society and consumers

Advertising has both desirable and undesirable effects. Clearly, the desired outcome of any advertising is to help sell products profitably. In addition to its economic role, advertising revenue supports an independent and diverse press, protected from government and interest group control. As a key communication link in the marketing process, it is also a major stimulus for stability and vigorous economic growth.

However, there is a growing awareness that advertising must go beyond fair and profitable interests. It is increasingly accepted that advertising must be designed in an atmosphere that considers a number of ethical vectors. For example, a recent study of advertising executives found that they face six fundamental ethical considerations in running their businesses:

- Treating customers fairly;
- Designing honest, fair, socially desirable advertising;
- Representing unhealthy, unnecessary or immoral products;
- Representing clients whose products/services are unhealthy, unnecessary or immoral;
- Dealing fairly with suppliers, sellers and the media;
- Dealing fairly with other agencies (K. Hung și M. Rice).

It is to the benefit of advertising and society in general that ethical issues are at the centre of the debate on advertising practice.

One of the most important roles of advertising is to show people how to solve problems. Effective advertising must start from the premise *"Does my product help people?"* It must reflect how a product relates to contemporary concerns. *"What are they thinking about, what are they worried about, what are your product's customers fighting for?"* Certain concerns such as health, money, raising children and relationships with other people are always important. *"Once you've identified the most pressing contemporary concerns, you can ask yourself how your product relates to reducing them."* (L.V. Strong). The literature shows that the main trend in modern advertising is to place the consumer at the centre of the marketing process. Companies believe that products are designed for the consumer, without the insistence of directing them (sometimes forcefully) to a pre-existing product that they cannot do without. Clearly, this process has led to fundamental, highly positive changes in advertising.

Satisfying and keeping customers

A buyer forms his own opinion of value and acts on it. His satisfaction or dissatisfaction after the purchase depends on the ratio in which the performance of the offer meets his expectations. We define consumer satisfaction as follows:

So, the level of satisfaction is a function determined by the difference between expectations and perceived performance. A buyer can experience one of two levels of satisfaction: if performance meets expectations, the consumer is satisfied; if performance exceeds expectations, he is fully satisfied.

There is a question that experts are asking themselves: "*how do consumer expectations arise?*", and the answer is based on previous buying experience, statements made by various acquaintances, as well as information and promises coming from the selling company and the competition. If a company sets buyer expectations too high, they are likely to be disappointed in the end.

Some of today's successful companies strive to raise expectations and deliver performance that matches them. Their goal is what is called TCS-Total Customer Satisfaction.

Companies not only place importance on improving relationships with supply chain partners, but also on establishing closer and more sustainable connections with end consumers.

In the past, customers were treated with a certain amount of indifference for a number of reasons: either because suppliers were few and buyers had limited choice, or because other suppliers provided services that were as poor in quality as the original supplier, or because the market was developing so fast that companies were not concerned with fully satisfying consumers. If a company was losing a hundred customers a week and gaining another hundred, its business was considered satisfactory. This reflected nothing more than a good 'movement' of the mass of customers, the costs involved being much higher than if the company had kept all its hundred customers without gaining any more.

Execution, cycle, and life stages of the product

In advertising, success depends as much on timely execution as it does on flawless product quality. Timeliness is an argument for both product execution and advertising. For example, many products have failed miserably, only to later witness success. For the same reason, it is often unprofitable for products that emerge in a late market to compete with established competitors.

Timeliness means, to paraphrase an advertising slogan, *to be a little ahead of the times*. Product innovations that address a new trend or a previously untapped need are those that are almost guaranteed to succeed. For more than two decades, companies have been striving to introduce interactive technology that will allow consumers to conduct a wide range of business from a personal computer. So far, these efforts have met with limited success, but the popularity of the Internet and the exploration of the Web offer realistic hope that the most ordinary consumers will go "online." A second element of advertising timeliness is determining the most appropriate opportunity to reach consumers for different products and services. The direct mail industry is adept at gathering information about the right time to launch a campaign for specific products. Although no two companies have the same problem, a general idea of when shoppers are most likely to make a particular purchase is valuable information for initiating advertising planning.

Therefore, the size of each stage needs to be reviewed periodically, as increased competition leads to shorter product life cycles, which means they need to generate profits in an ever-shorter time.

References:

- Abric, J. C. (2002) *Psihologia comunicării*, Iași: Polirom.
- Bertrand, C.-J. (coord.) (1995) *Médias*, Paris: Ellipses.
- Cathelat, B. (2005) *Publicitate și societate*, ediția a III-a, trad. de Costin Popescu, București: Editura TREI.
- Coman, C. (2001) *Relațiile publice. Principii și strategii*, Iași: Polirom.
- Coman, M. (1999) *Introducere în sistemul mass-media*, Iași: Polirom.
- David, G. (2002) *Relațiile publice – garanția succesului*, București: Editura Oscar Point.
- David, G. (2008) *Tehnici de relații publice*, Iași: Polirom.
- Morel, P. (1988) *Pratique des relations presse*, Paris: Dunod.
- Strong, V. L. (1990) *The How-to Book og Advertising*, Publicațiile Fairchild, Cambria.
- Scalabrini, E. C. B., Vaz, M., Teixeira, J. P., Rojo, C. J. R., Alonso, D. M., Mestre, L. G., & Fernandes, P. O. (2023). Residents' perceptions towards cross-border tourism. In *International Workshop Tourism and*

- Hospitality Management* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 129-139). ISAG-European Business School.
- Schubert, S. (2017). *Exploring the Ontological Nature of Teachers' Conversations Within a Dominant Ideology: A Hermeneutic Phenomenological Inquiry* (Doctoral dissertation, Flinders University, School of Education.).
- Stanescu, G. C. (2015). Media and the public opinion within the current political-economic context. *Annals of the University of Craiova for Journalism, Communication and Management*, 1(1), 42-49.
- Stănescu, G. C. (2016). The image of terrorism in european media a case study of four terrorist attacks. *Journal of Romanian Literary Studies*, (09), 664-669.
- Stanescu, G. C. (2022). The impact of virtual reality and augmented reality on storytelling. The future of journalism in metaverse. *Social Sciences and education research review*, 9(2), 115–118. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7474376>
- Stănescu, G. The challenges of journalistic deontology în pandemic crisis situations. *Recent trends in social sciences*, 69.
- Sujasan, S., & Wibowo, U. B. (2021). The Survival of School Financing Management in COVID-19 Pandemic. *Journal of Education and Learning (EduLearn)*, 15(4), 563-570.
- Taiwo, A. A., & Amusan, O. M. Communication and organization performance.
- Yurt, E. (2018). Sessizliğin Fenomenolojisi ya da Batı Düşünmesinde Özel bir Sessizlik Deneyiminin İzini Sürmek. *Isparta: Fakülte Kitabevi Yay.*